
Clinical Study Protocol Amendment: Appendix A

Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Appendix Edition Number	5
Appendix Date	21 October 2004

**Appendix A
Signatures**

ASTRAZENECA SIGNATURE(S)

JUPITER

**Justification for the Use of statins in Primary prevention: an Intervention Trial
Evaluatng Rosuvastatin**

**A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III
Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of
Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol
and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein**

This Clinical Study Protocol and all Amendments to the CSP have been subjected to an internal AstraZeneca peer review.

I agree to the terms of this study protocol/amendment.

AstraZeneca Research and Development
site representative

Product Medical Director, CRESTOR
AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals
1800 Concord Pike
P.O. Box 15437
Wilmington, DE

20 Oct 2004
Date
(Day Month Year)

This document contains confidential information, which should not be copied, referred to, released or published without written approval from AstraZeneca. Investigators are cautioned that the information in this protocol may be subject to change and revision.

Clinical Study Protocol Amendment

Amendment Number	04
Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Date	20 September 2005

JUPITER

Justification for the Use of statins in Primary prevention: an Intervention Trial Evaluating Rosuvastatin

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

This submission /document contains trade secrets and confidential commercial information, disclosure of which is prohibited without providing advance notice to AstraZeneca and opportunity to object.

Sponsor:

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP, 1800 Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

Centers affected by the Amendment:

All Centers

Reason for Amendment:

As recruitment has been slower than anticipated, the Jupiter study has been extended to additional countries, and the age limits have been lowered. The proposed change in age does not impact upon the validity of the study.

The amendment reflects updating of participating countries and study timelines; lowering of age limits for inclusion; clarifying visit procedures, criteria for end of study, and optional genetic analysis; revising excluded concomitant medications

Persons who initiated the Amendment:

AstraZeneca Clinical Study Team

The protocol for the study is to be amended as follows:

Section of protocol affected:

Cover page, AstraZeneca Research and Development Site Representative

Previous text:

[REDACTED]

Clinical Study Team Leader

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP

1800 Concord Pike [REDACTED]

Wilmington DE 19850-5437

[REDACTED]

Revised text:

[REDACTED]

Clinical Study Leader

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP

1800 Concord Pike [REDACTED]

Wilmington DE 19850-5437

[REDACTED]

Section of protocol affected:

Local Study Team contacts and Central Study Team contacts

Previous text:

Local Study Team contacts

Role in the study	Name	Address and Telephone Number
Local Study Team Leader/Monitor		

Role in the study	Name	Address and Telephone Number
Local Study Team Physician		
Local Study Team Drug Safety Representative (if applicable)		

Central Study Team contacts

Role in the study	Name	Address and Telephone number
Study Management Leader	[REDACTED]	AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP 1800 Concord Pike, D3B-113 Wilmington, DE 19850-5437 [REDACTED]
Clinical Study Team Physician	[REDACTED]	AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP 1800 Concord Pike, D3C-111 Wilmington, DE 19850-5437 [REDACTED]
24 hour emergency contact SAE Hotline	[REDACTED]	Pharmaceutical Product Development 3151 S. 17th Street Wilmington, NC 28412 [REDACTED]
Central Laboratory (USA)	Medical Research Laboratories International, USA	2 Tesseneer Drive Highland Heights, KY 41076 859- 781-8877
Central Laboratory (RoW)	MRLI, Europe	19 KleineKloosterstraat 1932 Zaventem Belgium +32 (0)2 725 2127
Interactive Voice Response System	Perceptive Informatics, Inc	900 Chelmsford Street Suite 308 Lowell, MA 01851 800-323-2996

Revised text:

Local Study Team contacts

Role in the study	Name	Address and Telephone Number
Local Study Team Leader/Monitor		
Local Study Team Physician		
Local Study Team Drug Safety Representative (if applicable)		
SAE Contact		
Central Laboratory		

Central Study Team contacts

Role in the study	Name	Address and Telephone number
Clinical Study Leader	██████████	AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP 1800 Concord Pike ██████████ Wilmington DE 19850-5437 ██████████
Clinical Study Team Physician	██████████	AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP 1800 Concord Pike, ██████████ Wilmington, DE 19850-5437 ██████████
Interactive Voice Response System	Perceptive Informatics, Inc	900 Chelmsford Street Suite 308 Lowell, MA 01851 800-323-2996

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Study center(s) and number of subjects planned

Previous text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female randomised subjects potentially recruited from the following areas:

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Germany – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Italy – approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 20 centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 40 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 5,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Lebanon – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Switzerland – approximately 300 subjects, approximately 30 centers

Revised text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female randomized subjects potentially recruited from the following areas:

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately **10** centers

Germany/Switzerland – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 40 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately **30** centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately **60** centers

Poland – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Russia – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 40 centers

South Africa – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Study period

Previous text:

Study period

Phase of development

Estimated date of first subject enrolled

February 2003

III

Estimated date of last subject completed

October 2008

Revised text:

Study period

Phase of development

Estimated date of first subject enrolled

February 2003

III

Estimated date of last subject completed

August 2010^a

^aThe revised date is subject to change based upon the rate of endpoint occurrences.

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Target subject population

Previous text:

This study will recruit men aged 55 years and older and women aged 65 years and older, who have no prior history of MI, stroke or arterial revascularization and who, on initial screening, are found to have LDL-C levels <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) and CRP levels ≥2.0 mg/L.

Revised text:

This study will recruit men aged **50 years** and older and women aged **60 years** and older, who have no prior history of MI, **unstable angina**, stroke or arterial revascularization and who, on initial screening, are found to have LDL-C levels <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) and CRP levels $\geq$ 2.0 mg/L.

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Duration of treatment

Previous text:

After a 4-week run-in period, subjects meeting the study inclusion criteria and having none of the exclusion criteria will be allocated to receive either rosuvastatin 20 mg/day or matching placebo until 520 events have occurred, which is expected to occur after a mean follow-up of approximately 3.5 years.

Revised text:

After a 4-week run-in period, subjects meeting the study inclusion criteria and having none of the exclusion criteria will be allocated to receive either rosuvastatin 20 mg/day or matching placebo until **at least 520 primary endpoints** have occurred.

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis, Statistical methods

Previous text:

A total of 15,000 subjects should be randomized to detect, with 90% power, a relative risk reduction as small as 25%. This assumes 3.5 year mean follow-up, a placebo event rate of 1.50 events per 100 patient-years-at-risk, and an annual 5% drop out/in rate. The study is scheduled to end when 520 primary endpoints have occurred. Planned interim analyses will be reviewed by the Independent Data Monitoring Board (IDMB). Statistical analysis of the primary endpoint will be based on the proportional hazards model using the Intention to Treat (ITT) population.

Revised text:

A total of 15,000 subjects should be randomized to detect, with 90% power, a relative risk reduction as small as 25%. This assumes 3.5 year mean follow-up, a placebo event rate of 1.50 events per 100 patient-years-at-risk, and an annual 5% drop out/in rate. The study is scheduled to end when **at least 520 primary endpoints** have occurred. Planned interim analyses will be reviewed by the Independent Data Monitoring Board (IDMB). Statistical analysis of the primary endpoint will be based on the proportional hazards model using the Intention to Treat (ITT) population.

Section of protocol affected:

1.2 Rationale for this study

Previous text:

Two landmark clinical trials, the Texas/Texas Coronary Atherosclerosis Prevention Study (AFCAPS/TexCAPS, Downs et al 1998) and the West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study (WOSCOPS, Shepherd et al 1995), clearly demonstrate that HMG-CoA reductase inhibition reduces the risk of first cardiovascular events. However, use of statins in the primary prevention of cardiovascular disease has not been widely adopted in part because the number of individuals who need to be treated to prevent 1 clinical event is relatively large, at least in comparison to secondary prevention (Goldman et al 1991).

Revised text:

Two landmark clinical trials, the **Air Force**/Texas Coronary Atherosclerosis Prevention Study (AFCAPS/TexCAPS, Downs et al 1998) and the West of Scotland Coronary Prevention Study (WOSCOPS, Shepherd et al 1995), clearly demonstrate that HMG-CoA reductase inhibition reduces the risk of first cardiovascular events. However, use of statins in the primary prevention of cardiovascular disease has not been widely adopted in part because the number of individuals who need to be treated to prevent 1 clinical event is relatively large, at least in comparison to secondary prevention (Goldman et al 1991).

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

Subjects will potentially be recruited from the following areas:

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Germany – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Italy – approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 20 centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 40 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 5,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Lebanon – approximately 500 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Switzerland – approximately 300 subjects, approximately 30 centers

Revised text:

Subjects will potentially be recruited from the following areas:

United States – approximately 8,000 subjects, approximately 800 centers

Canada - approximately 2,000 subjects, approximately 150 centers

Belgium – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Israel – approximately 200 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Estonia – approximately 100 subjects, approximately 15 centers

Latin America – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 200 centers

Denmark – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 10 centers

Germany/Switzerland – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 40 centers

Netherlands – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 30 centers

Norway – approximately 400 subjects, approximately 60 centers

Poland – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

Russia – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 100 centers

United Kingdom – approximately 3,000 subjects, approximately 40 centers

South Africa – approximately 1,000 subjects, approximately 50 centers

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

At 3 months, all randomised study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a blood sample will be obtained for safety assessment. Throughout the study, subjects will be

seen for study assessments at six-month intervals (see Table 4) for the duration of the study. All randomised subjects will be contacted by the site mid-way between their six-month visits regarding their study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed. All randomised subjects will have their final visit during the last 6 months of the study. Any randomised individual for which alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels are elevated up to >3 x upper limit normal (ULN) on 2 consecutive measurements 48 hours apart will be asked to discontinue study medication. As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that every randomised subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study drug per investigator discretion or subject preference. Subjects that have been discontinued from study drug and are unable to attend an office visit may complete their scheduled visits via telephone contact to ensure that adverse events and endpoints are identified and recorded.

Revised text:

At 3 months, all randomized study subjects will return for an initial Safety Visit; at this time a blood sample will be obtained for safety assessment. Throughout the study, subjects will be seen for study assessments at six-month intervals (see Table 4) for the duration of the study. All randomized subjects will be contacted by the site mid-way between their six-month visits regarding their **well-being, study medication administration**, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed. All randomized subjects will have their final visit during the last 6 months of the study. Any randomized individual for which alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels are elevated up to >3 x upper limit normal (ULN) on 2 consecutive measurements **at least** 48 hours apart will be asked to discontinue study medication. As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that every randomized subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study drug per investigator discretion or subject preference. Subjects that have been discontinued from study drug and are unable to attend an office visit may complete their scheduled visits via telephone contact to ensure that adverse events and endpoints are identified and recorded.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

All randomized study subjects will be followed until study completion (an estimated 5 year period) for the occurrence of a first ever acute cardiovascular event, defined as cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or arterial revascularization. At the time of the subject's first cardiovascular event, blinded study therapy will be discontinued. The subject will continue to follow scheduled study assessments until study completion and will be treated as deemed appropriate by the investigator.

Revised text:

All randomized study subjects will be followed until study completion (an estimated 5 year period, **or longer for early enrollers**) for the occurrence of a first ever acute cardiovascular event, defined as cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or

arterial revascularization. At the time of the subject's first cardiovascular event, blinded study therapy will be discontinued. The subject will continue to follow scheduled study assessments until study completion (**defined as at least 520 primary endpoints having occurred**) and will be treated as deemed appropriate by the investigator.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

There is a minimum of 10 study visits planned. Visits 1 and 2 occur during the placebo run-in period and Visits 3-10 occur during the randomized treatment period. Until the study closes, subjects who have completed Visit 10 but have not reached a study endpoint will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. During the final six months of the study, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F). For those randomised subjects in which study drug had previously been discontinued, a telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.

Revised text:

There is a minimum of 10 study visits planned. **Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit.** If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. **At the odd-numbered visits (10.1, 10.3, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (10.2, 10.4, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.** During the final six months of the study, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F). For those randomized subjects in which study drug had previously been discontinued, a telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

For Visits 2 and 3, the allowed visit window will be ± 3 days. For Visits 4 and 5, the allowed visit window will be ± 9 days. For Visits 6 onwards, the allowed visit window will be ± 10 days. If the date of an individual visit does not conform to the study plan and is therefore outside of the permitted visit window, the timing of subsequent visits should be planned to maintain the visit schedule relative to Visit 3, the Randomization Visit.

Revised text:

Visit 2 is allowed to take place within 17 days of Visit 1. For Visit 3, the allowed visit window will be ± 3 days. For Visits 4 and 5, the allowed visit window will be ± 9 days. For Visits 6 onwards, the allowed visit window will be ± 10 days. If the date of an individual visit does not conform to the study plan and is therefore outside of the permitted visit window, the timing of subsequent visits should be planned to maintain the visit schedule relative to Visit 3, the Randomization Visit.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart

Previous text:

None

Revised text:

If fingerstick testing (for cholesterol, CRP, glucose, or other) will be performed for the sole purpose of this study, informed consent must be obtained.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Screening Visit 1 (Week -6)

Previous text:

- If approved by the local regulatory authority, a screening informed consent will be obtained before any screening assessments are performed. If the subject is found to be eligible for the study, the subject will be asked to sign the main study consent form at Visit 2. If the screening informed consent is not approved by the local regulatory authority, the information contained in the screening informed consent and the main informed consent will be combined into one study informed consent form. If one main informed consent is used, the subject will sign at Visit 1 before any study related procedures are performed. (Please note that regardless of the type of study consent utilized, the consent for future genetic analysis addendum will not be obtained until Visit 2.)
- Subject eligibility assessed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of total cholesterol (TC), LDL-C, HDL-C, triglycerides (TG) and CRP

Revised text:

- If approved by the local regulatory authority, a screening informed consent will be obtained before any screening assessments are performed. If the subject is found to be eligible for the study, the subject will be asked to sign the main study consent form at Visit 2. If the screening informed consent is not approved by the local

regulatory authority, the information contained in the screening informed consent and the main informed consent will be combined into one study informed consent form. If one main informed consent is used, the subject will sign at Visit 1 before any study related procedures are performed.

- Subject eligibility assessed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of total cholesterol (TC), LDL-C, HDL-C, triglycerides (TG) and CRP

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Screening Visit 2 (Week –4)

Previous text:

- For those sites that are using a screening informed consent, full informed consent is obtained. This includes the addendum to the informed consent for those subjects who agree to have their samples stored for future genetic analysis. Consent to the genetic addendum is also obtained at this visit for those sites that are using only one consent.
- Inclusion/exclusion eligibility confirmed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of CRP, ALT, CK, Apolipoprotein (Apo) A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, TSH, fasting serum glucose (FSG), HbA_{1c} and complete blood count (CBC)

NOTE: Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for CRP and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in genomic and proteomic analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy. Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 2. To ensure participant confidentiality, these additional study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed.

- Urinalysis
- Physical exam performed
- Waist circumference taken
- Screening medical history obtained concerning cardiovascular risk factors, family history of premature coronary disease, and co-morbid conditions
- Adverse experiences assessed

- Endpoint and diabetes mellitus (DM) assessed
- Prior/current medications recorded
- Run-in study medication dispensed to subject
- Subjects who do not meet the entry criteria should be considered screen failures and a Screen Fail Case Report Form (CRF) should be completed

Revised text:

- For those sites that **used** a screening informed consent **form at Visit 1**, full informed consent **should subsequently be obtained at Visit 2**. This includes the **genetic addendum** to the informed consent for **all subjects to allow or disallow having** their samples stored for future genetic analysis. **For sites/countries who have informed AstraZeneca that they will be unable to participate in genetic analysis for all subjects, this genetic addendum is not applicable and need not be signed.**
- Inclusion/exclusion eligibility confirmed
- Fasting blood sample taken for analysis of CRP, ALT, CK, Apolipoprotein (Apo) A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, TSH, fasting serum glucose (FSG), HbA_{1c} and complete blood count (CBC)

The whole blood reserve sample collected at Visit 2 will be separated into plasma (for storage) and buffy coat sample (for genetic analysis). The buffy coat sample will not be processed or retained if the subject has not consented to this within the genetic informed consent addendum. Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for genetic analysis, cholesterol, CRP, and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy (specific analyses to be determined). To ensure participant confidentiality, these study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed.

NOTE for the U.S. and Canada: The genetic sample may be considered optional for some centers; however, the entire whole blood reserve sample is not optional in the U.S. and Canada.

NOTE for Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa: the buffy coat and plasma storage is considered optional.

- Urinalysis
- Physical exam performed

- Waist circumference taken
- Screening medical history obtained concerning cardiovascular risk factors, family history of premature coronary disease, and co-morbid conditions
- Adverse experiences assessed
- Endpoint and diabetes mellitus (DM) assessed
- Prior/current medications recorded
- Run-in study medication dispensed to subject
- Subjects who do not meet the entry criteria should be considered screen failures and a Screen Fail Case Report Form (CRF) should be completed

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Visit 6 (12-Month Visit)

Previous text:

- Study medication compliance checked
- Endpoint and DM assessed
- Adverse experiences assessed
- Concomitant medications recorded
- Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, CRP, ALT, and plasma reserve
- Urinalysis
- Study medication dispensed

Revised text:

- Study medication compliance checked
- Endpoint and DM assessed
- Adverse experiences assessed
- Concomitant medications recorded

- Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, creatinine, CRP, ALT, and plasma reserve (See also Section 7.6)
- Urinalysis
- Study medication dispensed

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Visits 10.1, 10.2, . . . etc. (if required)

Previous text:

Only for subjects who require prolonged follow-up. Assessments from Visit 9 repeated.

Revised text:

Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (10.1, 10.3, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (10.2, 10.4, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Figure 1 Study Flow Chart

Previous text:

Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 10.1	Visit F
Week-6	Week-4	Week-0	3Months	6Months	12 Months	18 Months	24 Months	30 Months	36 Months	Only if required*	Close-out Visit

Rosuvastatin 20 mg tabs

* If required, Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. will be done at 6-month intervals.

Revised text:

Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 10.1	Visit F
Week -6	Week -4	Week 0	3 Months	6 Months	12 Months	18 Months	24 Months	30 Months	36 Months	Only if required to reach study completion (520 endpoints)*	Close-out Visit

Rosuvastatin 20 mg tabs

* If required, Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. will be done at 6-month intervals.

Section of protocol affected:

3.1 Overall study design and flowchart, Table 4: Study Plan

Previous text:

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	F
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	52	78	104	130	156	182
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Randomization Visit	Safety Visit	Six- Month Visit	12 Month Visit	18 Month Visit	24 Month Visit	30 Month Visit	36 Month Visit	Close Out Visit
Eligibility Questionnaire	√	√	√								
Informed Consent	√	√									
Physical Exam		√									√
Waist Circumference		√									√
Screening Medical History		√									
Fasting Lipid Panel	√					√		√		√	√
C-reactive Protein ^a	√	√		√		√		√		√	√
ALT		√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
CK		√									√
TSH		√									
Serum Creatinine		√				√					√
Apo A-1/Apo B-100		√				√					√
Fasting Serum Glucose		√						√		√	√
HbA _{1c}		√						√		√	√
Hematology		√									√
Urinalysis		√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Drug		P ^b	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	
Endpoint and DM Assessment		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Prior/Concomitant Medications		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Adverse Event Assessment		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Compliance Check			√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≥ 2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

Revised text:

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 ^c	F					
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156 ^c	182
Visit Window		Within 17d of VI	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	Within final 6mo
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visit ^e	Close Out
Eligibility Questionnaire	√	√	√													
Informed Consent ^f	√	√														
Physical Exam																√
Waist Circumference																√
Screening Medical History																
Fasting Lipid Panel																√
C-reactive Protein ^a																√
ALT																√
CK																√
TSH																√
Serum Creatinine																√
Apo A-1/Apo B-100																√
Fasting Serum Glucose																√
HbA _{1c}																√
Hematology																√
Whole blood reserve sample (for plasma storage and optional buffy coat) ^g																√
Plasma storage sample ^h																√

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 ^c	F					
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156 ^c	182
Visit Window		Within 17d of V1	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d		±10d		±10d		±10d		±10d		Within final 6mo
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visit ^c	Close Out
Urinalysis	√			√	√		√		√		√		√		√	√
Drug		P ^b	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c	
Endpt & DM Assessment		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Prior/Concomitant Meds		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Adverse Event Assessment		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Compliance Check ⁱ			√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≥2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in.

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

^dTC represents a telephone contact.

^eUntil the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (10.1, 10.3, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (10.2, 10.4, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

^fInformed Consent should include genetic addendum, if applicable.

^gThe whole blood reserve sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa. In the U.S. and Canada, the whole blood reserve sample is not optional; however, the buffy coat will be discarded if the subject does not consent to participate in the genetic portion of the study.

^hPlasma storage sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa.

ⁱAt visits, pills will be counted; at phone calls, study drug administration will be verified.

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.2 Inclusion criteria

Previous text:

For inclusion in the study subjects must fulfill all of the following criteria:

1. Written informed consent to participate in the study (See Appendix B)
2. Men aged 55 years and over; women aged 65 years and over
3. Fasting LDL-C value <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) at Screening Visit 1
4. CRP value $\geq$ 2.0 mg/L at Screening Visit 1
5. TG <500 mg/dL (5.65 mmol/L) at Screening Visit 1

Revised text:

For inclusion in the study subjects must fulfill all of the following criteria:

1. Written informed consent to participate in the study (See Appendix B)
2. Men aged **50 years** and over; women aged **60 years** and over
3. Fasting LDL-C value <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) at Screening Visit 1
4. CRP value $\geq$ 2.0 mg/L at Screening Visit 1
5. TG <500 mg/dL (5.65 mmol/L) at Screening Visit 1

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.1 Criteria for discontinuation

Previous text:

Subjects may be discontinued from study medication at any time, at the discretion of the investigator(s). It is essential that every randomised subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study medication. Subjects who have been discontinued from study medication will complete their scheduled office visits, or may be contacted via phone by the site for the purpose of documenting endpoints. Specific reasons for discontinuing a subject from study medication are:

1. Withdrawal of informed consent

2. If, at any time, the subject's CK measures >10 x ULN and is accompanied by unexplained muscle pain, tenderness or weakness
3. If persistent ALT levels >3 x ULN are demonstrated
4. If there is deterioration in the subject's condition which, in the opinion of the investigator, warrants study medication withdrawal
5. If there is the occurrence of an adverse event which, in the opinion of the investigator, warrants study medication withdrawal
6. At the investigator's discretion

Revised text:

Subjects may be discontinued from study medication at any time, at the discretion of the investigator(s). It is essential that every randomized subject be followed for the duration of the study, including those that have been discontinued from study medication. Subjects who have been discontinued from study medication will complete their scheduled office visits, or may be contacted via phone by the site for the purpose of documenting endpoints. Specific reasons for discontinuing a subject from study medication are:

1. Withdrawal of informed consent
2. If, at any time, the subject's CK measures >10 x ULN and is accompanied by unexplained muscle pain, tenderness or weakness
3. If persistent ALT levels >3 x ULN **on two occasions at least 48 hours apart** are demonstrated
4. If there is deterioration in the subject's condition which, in the opinion of the investigator, warrants study medication withdrawal
5. If there is the occurrence of an adverse event which, in the opinion of the investigator, warrants study medication withdrawal
6. At the investigator's discretion

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.4.4 Procedures for Discontinuation

Previous text:

All adverse events must be reported, but in particular any adverse event leading to discontinuation from the study. All discontinuations due to a serious adverse event must be reported to AstraZeneca within 24 hours. **It is important that subjects who discontinue study medication continue to follow scheduled study assessments for the remainder of**

the study, on a six-month visit interval. If the subject is not able to attend an office visit, then a telephone contact may be done to ensure that subsequent cardiovascular events are identified and recorded.

Revised text:

All adverse events must be reported, but in particular any adverse event leading to discontinuation from the study. All discontinuations due to a serious adverse event must be reported to AstraZeneca within 24 hours. **It is important that subjects who discontinue study medication continue to follow scheduled study assessments for the remainder of the study, on a six-month visit interval, including between visit telephone contacts. If the subject is not able to attend an office visit, then a telephone contact may be done to ensure that subsequent cardiovascular events are identified and recorded.**

Section of protocol affected:

3.3.5 Restrictions

Previous text:

The following restrictions should be applied to subjects in this study:

1. Subjects should not be scheduled for Screening Visit 1 within 2 weeks of a major viral or bacterial illness
2. Subjects will fast (water is permitted) and refrain from alcohol consumption for 8 hours before Visits 6, 8, 10, and Close Out Visit
3. Subjects should be advised to maintain their normal physical activities or exercise routines during the study

Revised text:

The following **recommendations** should be applied to subjects in this study:

1. Subjects should not be scheduled for Screening Visit 1 within 2 weeks of a major viral or bacterial illness
2. Subjects will fast (water is permitted) and refrain from alcohol consumption for 8 hours before Visits **1, 2**, 6, 8, 10, and Close Out Visit
3. Subjects should be advised **not to change** their normal physical activities or exercise routines during the study

Section of protocol affected:

3.4.4.2 Methods for unblinding the study

Previous text:

The code may be broken only after a decision has been made to withdraw the subject from the study and if immediate knowledge of the study medication is needed to optimize the clinical management of the subject.

Revised text:

The code may be broken if immediate knowledge of the study medication is needed to optimize the clinical management of the subject. **After unblinding, the subject will be discontinued from study drug but is expected to continue to attend scheduled protocol visits for study assessments. The investigator must notify AstraZeneca of any code breaks and written records will be sent and archived.**

Section of protocol affected:

4.1 Primary Endpoint

Previous text:

The primary study endpoint will consist of the first occurrence of a major cardiovascular event after randomization; it will be either cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or arterial revascularization.

Revised text:

The primary study endpoint will consist of the first occurrence of a major cardiovascular event after randomization; it will be either cardiovascular death, stroke, myocardial infarction, unstable angina, or arterial revascularization. **At the time of the subject's first cardiovascular event, blinded study therapy will be discontinued. The subject will continue to follow scheduled study assessments until study completion (defined as at least 520 primary endpoints having occurred) and will be treated as deemed appropriate by the investigator.**

Section of protocol affected:

6.1 Determination of sample size

Previous text:

Estimates of required study sample size have been based on several considerations including expected event rate in the placebo group, anticipated relative risk reductions with rosuvastatin therapy, rates of non-study statin use, potential rates of annual losses to follow-up, and varying the length of study follow-up. In all calculations, required sample size has been based on a group-sequential design with an early stopping rule, an overall type 1 error probability of $\alpha = 0.05$ based on a 2-sided test of the equality of event rates in the 2 treatment groups, and a study power of 90%. Data that show alternative numbers of subjects required under alternative assumptions about event rates and effect size are provided in Table 6. The tables are based on the log-rank test under the additional assumption that subjects are recruited uniformly over a 1 year period.

Revised text:

Estimates of required study sample size have been based on several considerations including expected event rate in the placebo group, anticipated relative risk reductions with rosuvastatin therapy, rates of non-study statin use, potential rates of annual losses to follow-up, and varying the length of study follow-up. In all calculations, required sample size has been based on a group-sequential design with an early stopping rule, an overall type 1 error probability of $\alpha = 0.05$ based on a 2-sided test of the equality of event rates in the 2 treatment groups, and a study power of 90%. Data that show alternative numbers of subjects required under alternative assumptions about event rates and effect size are provided in Table 6. The tables are based on the log-rank test under the additional assumption that subjects are recruited uniformly over a 1-year period. **The sample size assumptions and estimates will be evaluated during the study, based on blinded data.**

Section of protocol affected:

6.1 Determination of sample size

Previous text:

The observed event rate in the placebo group is a major determinant of the power of the study. In analyses of primary prevention patients with low LDL-C and high CRP in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, the observed placebo event rate was just above 1 major cardiovascular event per 100 person-years of follow-up. However, this number is likely to be low for several reasons. First, the primary AFCAPS/TexCAPS endpoint did not include arterial revascularization procedures, an endpoint clearly reduced by statin therapy in other studies and a critical component of this study's endpoint; when these events from AFCAPS/TexCAPS are included, the base rate increases to 1.5 events/100 person-years of follow-up. Second, unlike AFCAPS/TexCAPS that enrolled men over age 45 and women over age 55, the current study includes only men over age 55 and women over age 65, a feature that should substantially increase absolute event rates. Similarly, and again in contrast with AFCAPS/TexCAPS, there is no upper age limit for eligibility in the current study. Third, the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study excluded individuals with markedly elevated body mass index. The inclusion of such subjects in this study should further increase absolute event rates in the placebo group. Last, the exclusion of women taking oral HRT will reduce the potential for misclassification bias on the basis of spurious CRP elevation. For all of these reasons, it is anticipated that the rate of event accrual should be 1.7 to 1.85 events/100 person years, a rate above that observed in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study. However, for the purposes of sample size determination, the study has been powered for a more conservative range of 1.35 to 1.50 events/100 person-years in the placebo arm.

A second key component of the sample size calculation is the expected relative risk reduction likely to be seen with daily oral rosuvastatin 20 mg. To date, with the sole exception of the Heart Protection Study, statin studies have generally reported 30 to 35% reductions in rates of acute coronary events in both secondary and primary prevention settings. In particular, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, the overall relative risk reduction was 37%, while that observed in the hypothesis-generating subgroup with low LDL-C/high CRP was 42%. It is important to

note that this level of relative risk reduction was achieved despite the fact that the agent tested was lovastatin, a first generation HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor with far less LDL reducing capacity than expected for rosuvastatin. By contrast, in the Heart Protection Study, the observed relative risk reduction was 24%. Although, when corrected for compliance it was equal to 33%. However, in that study which included many secondary prevention subjects, there was substantial crossover to active statin therapy in the placebo group. Despite these findings, for the purposes of sample size estimation, we have again taken a conservative view, and assumed a worst-case relative risk reduction for rosuvastatin of 25%.

Noncompliance and drop in/drop out are major challenges to the validity of any randomized study, and this third component of the sample size calculations also needs consideration. For example, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, study drug regimens were maintained over the mean follow-up of 5.2 years in 71% of actively treated patients and 63% of placebo treated patients. The observed 37% reduction in the primary endpoint occurred in spite of this level of non-compliance. Several design features of the proposed study, including the use of a pre-randomization compliance check in all potentially eligible study participants, should greatly reduce non-adherence throughout the follow-up period. In addition, in marked contrast to the Heart Protection Study, this study is focused on subjects well outside current NCEP ATP III guidelines for statin therapy and thus drop-in rates in the placebo group should be low. Specifically, while the Heart Protection Study included large numbers of subjects with known coronary disease, the current study is strictly of primary prevention subjects where medical community standards for statin prescription are much less aggressive. Second, entry criteria of an LDL-C <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) greatly reduces ethical concerns about placebo usage either at study initiation or during the estimated 3.5 year follow-up period. Finally, excluding those with diabetes helps ensure that crossover will not occur in this controversial high-risk subgroup.

The sample size tables show that across the range of reasonable event rates in the placebo group, the study must observe 514 events to have 90% power to detect a 25% reduction in this rate based on a 2-sided alpha of 0.05. We round this required number of events up to 520 total primary events. On the basis of these issues, we believe a total sample size of 12,000 participants would be adequate to detect with 90% power a relative risk reduction as small as 25% for an absolute placebo rate of 1.50 in a study with 3.5 year mean follow-up and a 5% annual loss rate (see Table 6). However, if the sample size is increased to 15,000, then almost all “worst-case” scenarios are covered, since such a study would be capable of detecting a relative risk reduction as small as 25% in a 4 year mean follow-up even if the placebo event rate is as low as 1.0 events per 100 person-years, a level below that observed in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which enrolled substantially younger patients.

Revised text:

The observed event rate in the placebo group is a major determinant of the power of the study. In analyses of primary prevention patients with low LDL-C and high CRP in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, the observed placebo event rate was just above 1 major cardiovascular event per 100 person-years of follow-up. However, this number is likely to be low for several reasons. First, the primary AFCAPS/TexCAPS endpoint did not include

arterial revascularization procedures, an endpoint clearly reduced by statin therapy in other studies and a critical component of this study's endpoint; when these events from AFCAPS/TexCAPS are included, the base rate increases to 1.5 events/100 person-years of follow-up. Second, unlike AFCAPS/TexCAPS that enrolled men over age 45 and women over age 55, the current study includes only men over **age 50** and women over **age 60**, a feature that should increase absolute event rates. Similarly, and again in contrast with AFCAPS/TexCAPS, there is no upper age limit for eligibility in the current study. Third, the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study excluded individuals with markedly elevated body mass index. The inclusion of such subjects in this study should further increase absolute event rates in the placebo group. Last, the exclusion of women taking oral HRT will reduce the potential for misclassification bias on the basis of spurious CRP elevation. For all of these reasons, it is anticipated that the rate of event accrual should be 1.7 to 1.85 events/100 person years, a rate above that observed in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study. However, for the purposes of sample size determination, the study has been powered for a more conservative range of 1.35 to 1.50 events/100 person-years in the placebo arm.

A second key component of the sample size calculation is the expected relative risk reduction likely to be seen with daily oral rosuvastatin 20 mg. To date, with the sole exception of the Heart Protection Study, statin studies have generally reported 30 to 35% reductions in rates of acute coronary events in both secondary and primary prevention settings. In particular, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, the overall relative risk reduction was 37%, while that observed in the hypothesis-generating subgroup with low LDL-C/high CRP was 42%. It is important to note that this level of relative risk reduction was achieved despite the fact that the agent tested was lovastatin, a first generation HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor with far less LDL reducing capacity than expected for rosuvastatin. By contrast, in the Heart Protection Study, the observed relative risk reduction was 24%. Although, when corrected for compliance it was equal to 33%. However, in that study which included many secondary prevention subjects, there was substantial crossover to active statin therapy in the placebo group. Despite these findings, for the purposes of sample size estimation, we have again taken a conservative view, and assumed a worst-case relative risk reduction for rosuvastatin of 25%.

Noncompliance and drop in/drop out are major challenges to the validity of any randomized study, and this third component of the sample size calculations also needs consideration. For example, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study, study drug regimens were maintained over the mean follow-up of 5.2 years in 71% of actively treated patients and 63% of placebo treated patients. The observed 37% reduction in the primary endpoint occurred in spite of this level of non-compliance. Several design features of the proposed study, including the use of a pre-randomization compliance check in all potentially eligible study participants, should greatly reduce non-adherence throughout the follow-up period. In addition, in marked contrast to the Heart Protection Study, this study is focused on subjects well outside current NCEP ATP III guidelines for statin therapy and thus drop-in rates in the placebo group should be low. Specifically, while the Heart Protection Study included large numbers of subjects with known coronary disease, the current study is strictly of primary prevention subjects where medical community standards for statin prescription are much less aggressive. Second, entry criteria of an LDL-C <130 mg/dL (3.36 mmol/L) greatly reduces ethical concerns about placebo

usage. Finally, excluding those with diabetes helps ensure that crossover will not occur in this controversial high-risk subgroup.

The sample size tables show that across the range of reasonable event rates in the placebo group, the study must observe 514 events to have 90% power to detect a 25% reduction in this rate based on a 2-sided alpha of 0.05. We round this required number of events up to 520 total primary events. On the basis of these issues, we believe a total sample size of 12,000 participants would be adequate to detect with 90% power a relative risk reduction as small as 25% for an absolute placebo rate of 1.50 in a study with 3.5 year mean follow-up and a 5% annual loss rate (see Table 6). However, if the sample size is increased to 15,000, then almost all “worst-case” scenarios are covered, since such a study would be capable of detecting a relative risk reduction as small as 25% in a 4 year mean follow-up even if the placebo event rate is as low as 1.0 events per 100 person-years, a level below that observed in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which enrolled younger patients.

Section of protocol affected:

6.2.3 Statistical analyses

Previous text:

The validity of the proportional hazards assumption will be tested through evaluation of a trend over time in the scaled Schoenfeld residuals. A violation of this assumption is unlikely because previous statin studies have found fairly uniform effects over time and the expected duration of follow-up in this study is 3.5 years. If a significant ($P < 0.01$) violation of the proportional hazards assumption is found, then estimates of the effects of rosuvastatin will be obtained from proportional hazards models fitted to data from each year of follow-up. However, the overall estimate from a single model fitted to all years of follow-up will continue to serve as the best single estimate of the treatment effects, especially in light of the low prior expectation of a changing effect over time.

Additional descriptive analyses will use the method of Kaplan and Meier to quantify the probability of remaining free of a primary study endpoint by time within each of the 2 treatment groups. Additional proportional hazards models will determine whether simultaneous control for baseline cardiovascular risk factors has any effect on the relative risk associated with treatment. Further, the distributions of major cardiovascular risk factors will be compared between treatment groups using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test for continuous variables and Chi-square tests for categorical variables.

Revised text:

The validity of the proportional hazards assumption will be tested through evaluation of a trend over time in the scaled Schoenfeld residuals. A violation of this assumption is unlikely because previous statin studies have found fairly uniform effects over time. If a significant ($P < 0.01$) violation of the proportional hazards assumption is found, then estimates of the effects of rosuvastatin will be obtained from proportional hazards models fitted to data from each year of follow-up. However, the overall estimate from a single model fitted to all years

of follow-up will continue to serve as the best single estimate of the treatment effects, especially in light of the low prior expectation of a changing effect over time.

Additional descriptive analyses will use the method of Kaplan and Meier to quantify the probability of remaining free of a primary study endpoint by time within each of the 2 treatment groups. Additional proportional hazards models will determine whether simultaneous control for baseline cardiovascular risk factors has any effect on the relative risk associated with treatment. Further, the distributions of major cardiovascular risk factors will be compared between treatment groups using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test for continuous variables and Chi-square tests for categorical variables. **Additional proportional hazards modeling will investigate the effects of the age-at-entry subgroups defined by men/women aged 55/65 years and over, respectively, versus men/women younger than 55/65 years, respectively.**

Section of protocol affected:

6.2.4 Interim analyses

Previous text:

To achieve the desired power, the study requires accrual of 520 primary endpoints. Thus, the study is designed to continue until both this number of primary outcomes is observed and the last randomized subject is followed for at least 3 years. However, 2 interim analyses are planned and the study will be terminated early if the early stopping rule is met and both the IDMB and the Steering Committee concur. A group sequential design will be used to preserve the overall type 1 error probability of 0.05.

Planned interim analyses will be performed when 37.5% of primary events have occurred (195 confirmed primary endpoints) and again when 75% of primary events have occurred (390 confirmed primary events). The final analysis is scheduled when 520 primary events have occurred. The group sequential boundaries for these 3 scheduled analyses are 2.947, 2.411, and 2.011, which correspond to nominal p-values of 0.003, 0.016, and 0.044, respectively. These boundaries are based on an alpha spending function that approximates an O'Brien-Fleming boundary in the setting of unequal analysis times. These information times were used, for example, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which was terminated early on the basis of a significant benefit found at the second interim analysis.

Revised text:

To achieve the desired power, the study requires accrual of **at least** 520 primary endpoints. However, 2 interim analyses are planned and the study will be terminated early if the early stopping rule is met and both the IDMB and the Steering Committee concur. A group sequential design will be used to preserve the overall type 1 error probability of 0.05.

Planned interim analyses will be performed when 37.5% of primary events have occurred (195 confirmed primary endpoints) and again when 75% of primary events have occurred

(390 confirmed primary events). The final analysis is scheduled when **at least 520** primary events have occurred. The group sequential boundaries for these 3 scheduled analyses are 2.947, 2.411, and 2.011, which correspond to nominal p-values of 0.003, 0.016, and 0.044, respectively. These boundaries are based on an alpha spending function that approximates an O'Brien-Fleming boundary in the setting of unequal analysis times. These information times were used, for example, in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which was terminated early on the basis of a significant benefit found at the second interim analysis.

Section of protocol affected:

7.6 Genetic sampling and storage

Previous text:

7.6 Genetic sampling and storage

Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for cholesterol, CRP, and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in genomic and proteomic analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy. Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 2. To ensure participant confidentiality, these additional study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed.

Revised text:

7.6 Genetic sampling and storage

The whole blood reserve sample collected at Visit 2 will be separated into plasma (for storage) and buffy coat sample (for genetic analysis). The buffy coat sample will not be processed or retained if the subject has not consented to this within the genetic informed consent addendum. Plasma and buffy coat samples obtained at Visit 2, in addition to being used for genetic analysis, cholesterol, CRP, and safety evaluations, will also be stored for future use in analyses relating to lipid metabolism, inflammatory function, and statin therapy (specific analyses to be determined). To ensure participant confidentiality, these study samples will be coded with separate participant identifiers during the course of the study and will be rendered fully anonymous after the study has been completed. Storage of the buffy coat sample and plasma reserve will not exceed 15 years after the completion of the study.

NOTE for the U.S. and Canada: The genetic sample may be considered optional for some centers; however, the entire whole blood reserve sample is not optional in the U.S. and Canada.

NOTE for Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa: the buffy coat and plasma storage is considered optional.

Section of protocol affected:

7.7 Volume of blood sampling and handling of biological samples

Previous text:

The total volume of blood that will be drawn from each subject in this study will not exceed the following:

Table 7 Volume of blood to be drawn from each subject

Assessment	Sample volume (ml)	Number of samples	Total volume (ml)
Lipid assay	7.5	5	37.5
CRP	7.5	7	52.5
HbA _{1c}	3.0	4	12.0
ALT	7.5	9	67.5
Clinical chemistry	7.5	2	15.0
Hematology	3.0	2	6.0
Plasma storage sample	5.0	1	5.0
Genetic testing	5.0	1	5.0
Total			200.0

The total volume of blood collected during the duration of the study is not expected to exceed 200.0 ml.

Revised text:

The total volume of blood that will be drawn from each subject in this study will not exceed the following:

Table 7 Volume of blood to be drawn from each subject

Assessment	Sample volume (ml)		Number of samples	Total volume (ml)	
	US & Canada	International ^a		US & Canada	International ^a
Lipid assay	7.5	8.5	5	37.5	42.5
CRP	2.5	3.5	7	17.5	24.5
HbA _{1c}	3.0	3.0	4	12.0	12.0
ALT	7.5	8.5	9	67.5	76.5
Clinical chemistry	7.5	8.5	2	15.0	17.0
Hematology	3.0	3.0	2	6.0	6.0
Plasma storage sample ^b	5.0	4.5	1	5.0	4.5
Whole blood reserve sample (for plasma storage and optional buffy coat) ^c	6.0	6.0	1	6.0	6.0
Total				166.5 ^d	189.0 ^d

^aInternational is inclusive of Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa.

^bPlasma storage sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa.

^cThe whole blood reserve sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa. In the U.S. and Canada, the whole blood reserve sample is not optional; however, the buffy coat will be discarded if the subject does not consent to participate in the genetic portion of the study.

^dThe actual total volume of blood drawn for the study will be less than that reflected in the table due to the fact that some assessments at certain visits are done from the same blood sample. Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. For each additional year the subject is in the study, these additional assessments will result in an additional 20.5ml of blood being collected for subjects in the U.S. & Canada and an additional 23.5ml of blood being collected for subjects in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, or Africa.

Section of protocol affected:

7.8 Study timetable and termination

Previous text:

The proposed start date for this study is February 2003. As such, recruitment is anticipated to end by December 2005 barring early termination by the IDMB. Database lock, which defines the end of the study, is anticipated in January 2009.

Revised text:

The **study started in** February 2003. As such, recruitment is anticipated to end by **August 2007^a** barring early termination by the IDMB. Database lock, which defines the end of the study, is anticipated in **December 2010^a**.

^aThe revised dates are subject to change based on the rate of endpoint occurrences.

Section of protocol affected:

8.3 Subject information and consent

Previous text:

The subject's signed and dated informed consent must be obtained before conducting any procedure specifically for the study.

The principal investigator(s) must store the original, signed Written Informed Consent Form. A copy of the Written Informed Consent Form must be given to the subject.

Revised text:

The subject's signed and dated informed consent must be obtained before conducting any procedure specifically for the study.

If fingerstick testing (for cholesterol, CRP, glucose, or other) will be performed for the sole purpose of this study, informed consent must be obtained.

The principal investigator(s) must store the original, signed Written Informed Consent Form. A copy of the Written Informed Consent Form must be given to the subject.

Section of protocol affected:

Appendix G: Management of Elevated Liver Enzymes

Previous text:

Statin-related ALT elevation is considered to be clinically significant if the ALT is increased to >3xULN on 2 consecutive occasions 48 hours apart. If this occurs without an obvious reversible precipitating factor, or if on clinical grounds, statin-induced liver disease is diagnosed or suspected, it is recommended that statin therapy should be discontinued. In these circumstances, and appropriate adverse event should be recorded, and the Study Team Physician must be informed

Revised text:

Statin-related ALT elevation is considered to be clinically significant if the ALT is increased to >3 x ULN on 2 consecutive occasions **at least** 48 hours apart. If this occurs without an obvious reversible precipitating factor, or if on clinical grounds, statin-induced liver disease is diagnosed or suspected, it is recommended that statin therapy should be discontinued. In

these circumstances, and appropriate adverse event should be recorded, and the Study Team Physician must be informed.

Section of protocol affected:

Appendix I: Disallowed Concomitant Medications

Previous text:

CLASS OF DRUG	GENERIC NAME
Antiobesity	Orlistat
Lipid regulation	niacin/nicotinic acid (includes vitamins / supplements with >50 mg niacin/nicotinic acid) probucol clofibrate cholestyramine except as specified in the protocol colesevelam hydrochloride colestipol hydrochloride except as specified in the protocol fenofibrate gemfibrozil atorvastatin lovastatin pravastatin simvastatin fluvastatin ezetimibe except as specified in the protocol fish oils (any dose) lipid lowering dietary supplements lipid lowering food additives
Immunosuppressants	lymphocyte immune globulin rho(d) immune globulin azathioprine sodium muromonab-CD3 cyclosporin rapamycin tacrolimus mycophenolate mofetil
Chronic use of steroids	prednisone, prednisolone, dexamethasone, hydrocortisone
Viral suppressants	protease inhibitors
Oral Hormone Replacement Therapy	estrogens progestins

Revised text:

CLASS OF DRUG	GENERIC NAME
Lipid regulation	niacin/nicotinic acid (includes vitamins / supplements with >50 mg niacin/nicotinic acid) probucol clofibrate cholestyramine except as specified in the protocol colesevelam hydrochloride colestipol hydrochloride except as specified in the protocol fenofibrate gemfibrozil atorvastatin lovastatin pravastatin simvastatin fluvastatin ezetimibe except as specified in the protocol
Immunosuppressants	lymphocyte immune globulin rho(d) immune globulin azathioprine sodium muromonab-CD3 cyclosporin rapamycin tacrolimus mycophenolate mofetil
Chronic use of steroids	prednisone, prednisolone, dexamethasone, hydrocortisone
Oral Hormone Replacement Therapy	estrogens progestins

Clinical Study Protocol Amendment: Appendix A

Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Appendix Edition Number	6
Appendix Date	20 September 2005

**Appendix A
Signatures**

ASTRAZENECA SIGNATURE(S)

JUPITER

**Justification for the Use of statins in Primary prevention: an Intervention Trial
Evaluating Rosuvastatin**

**A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III
Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of
Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol
and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein**

This Clinical Study Protocol and all Amendments to the CSP have been subjected to an internal AstraZeneca peer review.

I agree to the terms of this study protocol/amendment.

AstraZeneca Research and Development
site representative

27 SEP 2005

Date

Executive Director, Clinical Development (Day Month Year)
Medical Science Director, CRESTOR
AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals
1800 Concord Pike
P.O. Box 15437
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

This document contains confidential information, which should not be copied, referred to, released or published without written approval from AstraZeneca. Investigators are cautioned that the information in this protocol may be subject to change and revision.

2(3)

CV.000-259-161.2.0 (Version Created 26 Sep 2005 20:25:23)

Section 5.3.5.1.1 /p.163

Clinical Study Protocol Administrative Change

Change No.	01
Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Edition No.	03
Date	27 April 2004

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Sponsor:

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP, 1800 Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437.

Centres affected by the Administrative Change

This administrative change affects all centres in the study.

The protocol for the study is to be changed as follows:

Section of the protocol affected:

Protocol Title

Previous Text:

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of **Rosuvastatin (Crestor®)** 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Revised Text:

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of **Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®)** 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Section of the protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis Title

Previous Text:

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo Controlled, Multicenter, Phase II Study of **Rosuvastatin (Crestor®)** 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subject with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Revised Text:

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo Controlled, Multicenter, Phase II Study of **Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®)** 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subject with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

Section of protocol affected:

Protocol Synopsis

Previous text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female subjects recruited **from the United States (approximately 400 centers) and from Canada (approximately 100 centers). It is planned to recruit approximately 30 subjects per center.**

Revised text:

This study will be conducted in approximately 15,000 male and female subjects recruited **from the United States (up to 800 centers) and from Canada (up to 250 centers).**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

Subjects will be recruited **from the United States (approximately 400 centers) and from Canada (approximately 100 centers); each center will recruit approximately 30 subjects.**

Revised text:

Subjects will be recruited **from the United States (up to 800 centers) and from Canada (up to 250 centers).**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Screening Visit 1 (Week -6)

Previous text:

Full informed consent taken before any assessments; this includes the addendum to the informed consent for those subjects who agree to have their samples stored for future genetic analyses.

Revised text:

A screening informed consent will be obtained before any screening assessments are performed. If the subject is found to be eligible for the study, then the subject will be asked to sign the main study consent before continuing in the study.

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Screening Visit 2 (Week -4)

New text:

Full informed consent taken; this includes the addendum to the informed consent for those subjects who agree to have their samples stored for future genetic analyses.

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Screening Visit 2 (Week -4), Paragraph 1

Previous text:

Samples for genetic analyses will be retained **only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 1.**

Revised text:

Samples for genetic analyses will be retained **only for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 2.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Safety Visit 4 (3-Month Visit)

Previous text:

Fasting blood samples taken for CRP and ALT

Revised text:

Blood samples taken for CRP and ALT

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1, Overall study design and flow chart, Visit 6 (12-Month Visit)

Previous text:

Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, CRP, ALT and plasma reserve.

Revised text:

Fasting blood samples taken for analysis of TC, LDL-C, HDL-C, TG, Apo A-1 and Apo B-100, **creatinine**, CRP, ALT and plasma reserve.

Section of protocol affected:

Table 4, Study Plan

Previous Text: Table 4 Study plan

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	F
Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	F
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	52	78	104	130	156	182
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Randomization Visit	Safety Visit	Six-Month Visit	12 Month Visit	18 Month Visit	24 Month Visit	30 Month Visit	36 Month Visit	Close Out Visit
Eligibility Questionnaire	✓	✓	✓								
Informed Consent	✓										
Physical Exam		✓									✓
Waist Circumference		✓									✓
Screening Medical History		✓									
Fasting Lipid Panel	✓					✓		✓		✓	✓
C-reactive Protein ^a	✓			✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
ALT		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
CK		✓									✓
TSH		✓									
Serum Creatinine		✓									✓
Apo A-1/Apo B-100		✓				✓					✓
Fasting Serum Glucose		✓						✓		✓	✓
HbA _{1c}		✓						✓		✓	✓
Hematology		✓									✓
Urinalysis		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Drug		P ^b		P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c		P/R ^c	
Endpoint and DM Assessment		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Prior/Concomitant Medications		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Adverse Event Assessment		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Compliance Check				✓		✓		✓		✓	✓

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≥2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

Revised Text: Table 4 Study plan

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	F
Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	F
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	52	78	104	130	156	182
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Randomization Visit	Safety Visit	Six-Month Visit	12 Month Visit	18 Month Visit	24 Month Visit	30 Month Visit	36 Month Visit	Close Out Visit
Eligibility Questionnaire	✓	✓	✓								
Informed Consent	✓	✓									
Physical Exam		✓									✓
Waist Circumference		✓									✓
Screening Medical History		✓									
Fasting Lipid Panel	✓					✓		✓		✓	✓
C-reactive Protein ^a	✓			✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
ALT		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
CK		✓									✓
TSH		✓									
Serum Creatinine		✓				✓					✓
Apo A-1/Apo B-100		✓				✓					✓
Fasting Serum Glucose		✓						✓		✓	✓
HbA _{1c}		✓						✓		✓	✓
Hematology		✓									✓
Urinalysis		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Drug		P ^b	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c	P/R ^c
Endpoint and DM Assessment		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Prior/Concomitant Medications		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Adverse Event Assessment		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Compliance Check			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≥ 2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.3.4.3, Incorrectly enrolled or randomised subjects, Paragraph 2

Previous text:

In all other instances, incorrectly enrolled subject **will be discontinued from further study treatment and assessments.**

Revised text:

In all other instances, incorrectly enrolled subjects **will be discontinued from further study treatment and assessments if this will be associated with risk or discomfort for these subjects.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.3.4.4, Procedures for discontinuation, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

It is important that subjects who discontinue study medication continue to follow scheduled study assessments **for the remainder of the study, on a six-month visit interval, to ensure that subsequent cardiovascular events are identified and recorded.**

Revised text:

It is important that subjects who discontinue study medication continue to follow scheduled study assessments **for the remainder of the study, on a six-month visit interval. If the subject is not able to attend an office visit, then a telephone contact may be done to ensure that subsequent cardiovascular events are identified and recorded.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.3.5, Restrictions

Previous text:

Subjects who are blood donors should not donate blood during the study and for 3 months following their last dose of study treatment.

Revised text:

Bullet deleted

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.3.5, Restrictions

Previous text:

Subjects will fast (water is permitted) and **refrain from alcohol consumption for 8 hours before each visit.**

Revised text:

Subjects will fast (water is permitted) and **refrain from alcohol consumption for 8 hours before Visits 6, 8, 10 and Close Out Visit.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 4.4.3.1, Methods of assessment, Paragraph 7

Previous text:

In addition, **CK and creatinine will be measured at Visit F.**

Revised text:

In addition, **creatinine will be obtained at Visit 6 and Visit F. CK will also be measured at Visit F.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 6.3, Independent Data Monitoring Board, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

An IDMB will review unblended safety data approximately twice a year and **will include evaluations of all laboratory data, qualify assurance reports, and serious adverse experiences** defined as those (1) requiring or prolonging hospitalization, (2) resulting in a permanent or substantial disability, and (3) deaths.

Revised text:

An IDMB will review unblinded safety data approximately twice a year and **will include tables of laboratory data, concomitant medications, adverse events and serious adverse experiences** defined as those (1) requiring or prolonging hospitalization, (2) resulting in a permanent or substantial disability, and (3) deaths.

Section of protocol affected:

Section 7.6, Genetic sampling and storage, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only **for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 1.**

Revised text:

Samples for genetic analyses will be retained only **for those subjects who have signed the addendum to the informed consent at Visit 2.**

Section of protocol affected:

Section 7.8, Study timeline and termination, Paragraph 1

Previous text:

As such, **recruitment is anticipated to end by July 2004 with an expected study completion by December 2007**, barring early termination by the IDMB.

Revised text:

As such, **recruitment is anticipated to end by December 2005**, barring early termination by the IDMB.

Section of protocol affected:

Appendix E

Previous Text:

INSURANCE AND INDEMNITY

AstraZeneca's liability is covered by a liability insurance policy with AstraZeneca Insurance Company Limited, policy NO.: L/702938.

Revised Text:

INSURANCE AND INDEMNITY*

AstraZeneca's liability is covered by a liability insurance policy, please contact your AstraZeneca representative for further information.

***For studies conducted in the US and Canada, this Appendix Insurance and Indemnity is not applicable. Please refer to the clinical study agreement for information concerning AstraZeneca's obligation to insure and indemnify the Institution and investigator.**

Reason for Administrative Change:

The reason for this administrative change is to increase the number of centers, modify the informed consent process, add a creatinine analysis, clarify the process for incorrectly enrolled and discontinued subjects, remove the blood donation restriction, clarify the fasting restriction, clarify the IDMB review, revise the anticipated end of the recruitment period and clarify the insurance and indemnity information.

Persons who initiated the Administrative Change:

[Redacted] Clinical Study Leader

Signed agreement to the Administrative Change:

I hereby approve the Administrative Change to the Clinical Study Protocol.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

13 May 2004

Date
(Day month, year)

[Redacted]
AstraZeneca Clinical Study Team Leader
Christina DiCocco, AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals, Room [Redacted] 1800
Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437.

THIS IS A PRINTED COPY OF AN ELECTRONIC DOCUMENT. PLEASE CHECK ITS VALIDITY BEFORE USE.

10(11)

Clinical Study Protocol Administrative Change No. 01
Study code 4522US/0011

Signed agreement to the Administrative Change:

I hereby approve the Administrative Change to the Clinical Study Protocol.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

.....
Date
(Day month, year)

.....
AstraZeneca Local Study Team

Clinical Study Protocol Administrative Change

Change No.	02
Drug Substance	Rosuvastatin
Study Code	4522US/0011
Edition No.	01
Date	20 March 2007

A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter, Phase III Study of Rosuvastatin (CRESTOR®) 20 mg in the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events Among Subjects with Low Levels of LDL-Cholesterol and Elevated Levels of C-Reactive Protein

This submission /document contains trade secrets and confidential commercial information, disclosure of which is prohibited without providing advance notice to AstraZeneca and opportunity to object.

Sponsor:

AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP, 1800 Concord Pike, Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

Centres affected by the Administrative Change

All Centers

The protocol for the study is to be changed as follows:

This administrative change has been completed for clarification of the protocol. No protocol amendment will accompany this document.

Section of protocol affected:

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart page 21 paragraph 6 and page 25, paragraph 2; Section 3.1 Study Flow Chart Figure 1, Study Plan table 4; Section 3.3.4.2 Voluntary discontinuation by a subject; Section 6.1 Determination of sample size.

Previous text:

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart

There is a minimum of 10 study visits planned. Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at

six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (10.1, 10.3, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (10.2, 10.4, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed. During the final six months of the study, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F). For those randomized subjects in which study drug had previously been discontinued, a telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.

Revised text:

There is a minimum of 10 study visits planned. Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit **11, 12**, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (**11, 13, etc.**), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (**12, 14, etc.**), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed. During the final six months of the study, all subjects will attend the clinic for their final visit (Visit F). For those randomized subjects in which study drug had previously been discontinued, a telephone contact may be made if the subject is unable to attend an office visit.

Previous text:

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart

Visits 10.1, 10.2, . . . etc. (if required)

Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (10.1, 10.3, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (10.2, 10.4, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

Revised text:

Visits 11, 12, . . . etc. (if required)

Until the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered **Visit 11, 12, etc.** At the odd-numbered **visits (11, 13, etc.)**, the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered **visits (12, 14, etc.)**, the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

Previous text:

Section 3.1 Overall study design and flow chart

Study Flow Chart Figure 1

Figure 1 Study Flow Chart

Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 10.1	Visit F
Week - 6	Week - 4	Week 0	3 Months	6 Months	12 Months	18 Months	24 Months	30 Months	36 Months	Only if required to reach study completion (520 endpoints)*	Close-out Visit

Rosuvastatin 20 mg tabs

* If required, Visit 10.1, 10.2, etc. will be done at 6-month intervals.

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	Study Plan										F					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	TCd		10e				
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156e	182
Visit Window		Within 17d of V1	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	Within final 6mo
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visit	Close Out
Eligibility Questionnaire	✓	✓	✓													
Informed Consent	✓	✓														
Physical Exam		✓														✓
Waist Circumference		✓														✓
Screening Medical History		✓														
Fasting Lipid Panel	✓						✓				✓				✓	✓
C-reactive Proteina	✓			✓			✓				✓				✓	✓
ALT		✓		✓			✓		✓		✓				✓	✓
CK		✓														✓
TSH		✓														
Serum Creatinine		✓					✓									✓
Apo A-1/Apo B-100		✓					✓									✓
Fasting Serum Glucose		✓						✓							✓	✓
HbA1c		✓						✓							✓	✓

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	TCd	10e	F				
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	104	130	143	156e	182				
Visit Window		Within 17d of V1	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d		±10d	Within final 6mo				
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visit	Close Out
Hematology	✓															✓
Whole blood reserve sample (for plasma storage and optional buffy coat)g	✓															
Plasma storage sampleh						✓										
Urinalysis	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Drug	Pb		P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc
Endpt & DM Assessment	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Prior/Concomitant Meds	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Adverse Event Assessment	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Compliance Check i			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≤ 2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in.

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

^dTC represents a telephone contact.

^eUntil the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 11, 12, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (11, 13, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (12, 14, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

^fInformed Consent should include genetic addendum, if applicable.

^gThe whole blood reserve sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa. In the U.S. and Canada, the whole blood reserve sample is not optional; however, the buffy coat will be discarded if the subject does not consent to participate in the genetic portion of the study.

^hPlasma storage sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa.

ⁱAt visits, pills will be counted; at phone calls, study drug administration will be verified.

Revised text:

Figure 2 Study Flow Chart

Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 11	Visit F
Week - 6	Week - 4	Week 0	3 Months	6 Months	12 Months	18 Months	24 Months	30 Months	36 Months	Only if required to reach study completion (520 endpoints)*	Close-out Visit

Rosuvastatin 20 mg tabs

* If required, **Visit 11, 12**, etc. will be done at 6-month intervals.

Study Plan table 4

Table 4	Study Plan															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	TCd	10e/j	F				
Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	TCd	10e/j	F				
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156e/j	182
Visit Window		Within 17d of V1	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d						±10d	Within final 6mo
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visite/j	Close Out
Eligibility Questionnaire	✓	✓	✓													
Informed Consent f/j	✓	✓													*j	✓
Physical Exam		✓														✓
Waist Circumference		✓														✓
Screening Medical History		✓														
Fasting Lipid Panel	✓										✓	✓			✓	✓
C-reactive Proteina	✓										✓	✓			✓	✓
ALT		✓									✓	✓			✓	✓
CK		✓									✓	✓			✓	✓
TSH		✓														
Serum Creatinine		✓														
Apo A-1/Apo B-100		✓														
Fasting Serum Glucose		✓										✓			✓	✓
HbA1c		✓										✓			✓	✓
Hematology		✓														✓

Table 4 Study Plan

Visit Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	TCd	10e/j	F				
Week No.	-6	-4	0	13	26	39	52	65	78	91	104	117	130	143	156e/j	182
Visit Window		Within 17d of V1	±3d	±9d	±9d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	±10d	Within final 6mo
	Screen Visit 1	Screen Visit 2	Rand Visit	Safety Visit	6 Mo Visit	9 Mo Contact	12 Mo Visit	15 Mo Contact	18 Mo Visit	21 Mo Contact	24 Mo Visit	27 Mo Contact	30 Mo Visit	33 Mo Contact	36 Mo Visit/e/j	Close Out
Whole blood reserve sample (for plasma storage and optional buffy coat) g	✓						✓									
Plasma storage sample ^h							✓									
Urinalysis		✓		✓	✓		✓		✓		✓		✓		✓	
Drug		Pb	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc	P/Rc		P/Rc		P/Rc		P/Rc		P/Rc	
End pt & DM Assessment		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Prior/Concomitant Meds		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Adverse Event Assessment		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Compliance Check i			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

^aC-reactive protein (CRP) to be measured at Visit 1 must be ≥2.0 mg/L

^bAll potential participants to receive single-blind placebo therapy during 4 week compliance run-in.

^cP = placebo, R = rosuvastatin

^dTC represents a telephone contact.

^eUntil the study closes (at least 520 primary endpoints have occurred), subjects who have completed Visit 10, who have either not had a study endpoint, or have had an endpoint and continue to be followed, will be asked to return at six-month intervals to repeat the assessments conducted at Visit 9 and Visit 10, alternating until the final visit. If these additional visits are required, they will be numbered Visit 11, 12, etc. At the odd-numbered visits (11, 13, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 9 should be performed, and at the even-numbered visits (12, 14, etc.), the assessments listed for Visit 10 should be performed. All randomized subjects will continue to be contacted by the site mid-way between these additional visits regarding their well-being, study medication administration, study participation, and to confirm their address has not changed.

^fInformed Consent should include genetic addendum, if applicable.

^gThe whole blood reserve sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa. In the U.S. and Canada, the whole blood reserve sample is not optional; however, the buffy coat will be discarded if the subject does not consent to participate in the genetic portion of the study.

^hPlasma storage sample is optional for sites in Europe, Middle East, Latin America, and Africa.

ⁱAt visits, pills will be counted; at phone calls, study drug administration will be verified.

Subjects who have discontinued study drug and who do not wish to participate in routine study assessments will be given the option to be followed by phone until the end of the study. However, vital status will be confirmed on all randomized subjects at the end of study.

Previous text:

3.3.4.2 Voluntary discontinuation by a subject

Subjects who request to discontinue from the study should always be asked about the reason(s) for their discontinuation and about the presence of any endpoints or adverse events. If possible, they should be seen and assessed by an investigator(s). Adverse events should be followed up and investigational products should be returned by the subject. At the time the subject expresses his/her desire to withdraw from the study, the study staff should ascertain from the subject whether the subject truly wishes to withdraw from the study entirely, or just discontinue study medication. Subjects who discontinue study medication have the option of being followed up by phone contact in accordance with their visit schedule if they are unable to attend office visits. Study medication may be restarted at any time unless contraindicated. As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that all randomized subjects be followed for the course of the study in order to document endpoints and vital status.

Revised text:

Subjects who request to discontinue from the study should always be asked about the reason(s) for their discontinuation and about the presence of any endpoints or adverse events. If possible, they should be seen and assessed by an investigator(s). Adverse events should be followed up and investigational products should be returned by the subject. At the time the subject expresses his/her desire to withdraw from the study, the study staff should ascertain from the subject whether the subject truly wishes to withdraw from the study entirely, or just discontinue study medication. Subjects who discontinue study medication have the option of being followed up by phone contact in accordance with their visit schedule if they are unable to attend office visits. Study medication may be restarted at any time unless contraindicated. As this is an endpoint study, it is essential that all randomized subjects be followed for the course of the study in order to document endpoints and vital status. **Vital status for all randomized subjects will be confirmed at the end of the study in accordance with the protocol.**

Previous Text:

6.1 Determination of sample size

The sample size tables show that across the range of reasonable event rates in the placebo group, the study must observe 514 events to have 90% power to detect a 25% reduction in this rate based on a 2-sided alpha of 0.05. We round this required number of events up to 520 total primary events. On the basis of these issues, we believe a total sample size of 12,000 participants would be adequate to detect with 90% power a relative risk reduction as small as 25% for an absolute placebo rate of 1.50 in a study with 3.5 year mean follow-up and a 5% annual loss rate (see Table 6). However, if the sample size is increased to 15,000, then almost all “worst-case” scenarios are covered, since such a study would be capable of detecting a relative risk reduction as small as 25% in a 4 year mean follow-up even if the placebo event rate is as low as 1.0 events per 100 person-years, a level below that observed in the

AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which enrolled younger patients.

Revised Text:

The sample size tables show that across the range of reasonable event rates in the placebo group, the study must observe 514 events to have 90% power to detect a 25% reduction in this rate based on a 2-sided alpha of 0.05. We round this required number of events up to 520 total primary events. On the basis of these issues, we believe a total sample size of 12,000 participants would be adequate to detect with 90% power a relative risk reduction as small as 25% for an absolute placebo rate of 1.50 in a study with 3.5 year mean follow-up and a 5% annual loss rate (see Table 6). However, if the sample size is increased to 15,000, then almost all “worst-case” scenarios are covered, since such a study would be capable of detecting a relative risk reduction as small as 25% in a 4 year mean follow-up even if the placebo event rate is as low as 1.0 events per 100 person-years, a level below that observed in the AFCAPS/TexCAPS study which enrolled younger patients. **The final number of subjects randomized in this trial was 17,802. This number ensures and falls within the scenarios covered in table 6.**

Reason for Administrative Change:

The enrollment for this trial is complete and final number of subjects randomized was 17,802. This number falls within the scenarios covered in table 6 of Clinical study protocol, thus allowing additional robustness to the study.

Bulgaria and Romania are also participating in this trial.

The administrative change clarifies the intent of the protocol and the need to collect the vital status of all randomized subjects at the end of study. The final vital status confirmation can be obtained by phone or by site searches as outlined in the protocol.

The visit numbering scheme was modified to accommodate the extension of the visit schedule, for visits exceeding visit 10.

The study flow chart and study plan have been updated to reflect the clarifications included in this administrative change.

Persons who initiated the Administrative Change:

AstraZeneca Clinical Study Team

Signed agreement to the Administrative Change:

Senior Director, Clinical Research
Study Team Physician
AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

Study Delivery Program Leader
AstraZeneca Pharmaceuticals LP
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

I hereby approve the Administrative Change to the Clinical Study Protocol.

Study Code: 4522US/0011

26 April 2007

Date
(Day month, year)

Senior Director, Clinical Research
Study Team Physician
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437

Signed agreement to the Administrative Change:

I hereby approve the Administrative Change to the Clinical Study Protocol.

Study Code: 4522US/00

26 April 2007

Date
(Day month, year)

AstraZeneca Study Delivery Program Leader
1800 Concord Pike
Wilmington, DE 19850-5437